

State Obligations and the Protection of the Rights of Prisoners in Cameroon: A Legal Perspective

Sone Patience Munge, PhD.,¹ & Wabi Wilson Wakai, PhD.²

¹Professor of Law, Faculty of Laws and Political Science, University of Buea, Cameroon.

Email: pattysonem@gmail.com

*²Lecturer, Department of English Law, Faculty of Laws and Political Science,
University of Buea, Cameroon. Corresponding author.*

Email: Wabi.wilson@ubuea.cm

Abstract:

Protecting Prisoners' Rights remains a complex situation in most societies given the crimes they have committed. However, it must be underscored that people are sentence to prison as punishment and not for punishment. This therefore invokes the issue of state obligations, most especially positive obligations towards prisoners. States all claim to realise these obligations. However, violations of the rights of prisoners continue to increase with most states not meeting up their obligations under international human rights instruments protecting the rights of prisoners. This paper examines the rights of prisoners in Cameroon and analyses the challenges faced by Cameroon in meeting up to her obligations. It adopts a doctrinal approach with the use of content analysis and interpretation of primary and secondary sources of information. The study is underpinned by the triple pronged theory of Henry Shue whereby States must respect, protect and fulfil the rights of prisoners under ratified International Human Rights Norms. The study argues that prisoners' rights are not novel category of rights and therefore concludes that Cameroon is yet to effectively engage in her efforts to protect the rights of prisoners' and thus not effectively realising the obligations to respect, protect and fulfil.

Keywords: Cameroon, Detention conditions, Prisoners' Rights, Protection, Challenges.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons

Attribution International
License (CC BY 4.0).

1. INTRODUCTION

The world's Prisoners population stands at over 9 million¹ and one out of every 700 people in the world is in the correctional center². It is for this reason that prisoners' rights are protected at both domestic and international levels. The international protection of these rights emanates from the principle that prisoners do not part with their rights when they enter the prisons³. This means that they must not be subjected to physical, mental abuse and inhuman conditions in the prisons. It is noteworthy that prisoners' rights are first of all human rights. Any discussion of the protection of such rights has to be viewed in that context.

The preamble to the 1996 constitution of Cameroon proceeds in two ways of consecrating human rights. The first being that an adhesion consecration as it provides that the people of Cameroon solemnly proclaim attach themselves to ideas and human rights as proclaimed by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights⁴ (UDHR) 1948 and other ratified conventions on human rights⁵. Secondly, there is a list of consecration of rights and freedoms that the state is enjoined to respect and protect within the preamble. These are generally rights belonging to the first and second generations of human rights without specific reference to any group therein⁶. Article 65 of the same constitution provides on this perspective that the preamble shall be part and parcel of the constitution. This is an exception to the general rule that preambles of constitutions donot form part of the constitution.

The protection of prisoners rights in Cameroon is embeded in the Constitution⁷ and the constitution remains the *grund norm* wherein other efforts to protect prisoners rights originate⁸. This constitution, for the first time in the history of Cameroon Human

¹ R. Walmsley, *World Prison Population List*, (6th ed), International Centre for Prison Studies (2005) p, 14.

² R. Walmsley, "Global incarceration and prison trends", *Forum on Crime and Society* (2003), 3 (1/2), 65-67 at 67.

³ Principle 5 of the Basic Principles for the Treatment of Prisoners adopted and proclaimed by General Assembly Resolution 45/111 of 14 December 1990. The Human Rights Committee on the rights of persons deprived of their liberty, General Comment 21, Article 10 (Forty-fourth session, (1992), Compilation of General Comments and General Recommendations Adopted by Human Rights Treaty Bodies, U.N. Doc. HRI/GEN/1/Rev.1 at 33 (1994) para 3.

⁴ Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by General Assembly Resolution 217 A (III), proclaimed by the United Nations General Assembly in Paris on 10 December 1948.

⁵ Examples of these ratified conventions include the ICCPR 1966, ICESCR 1966, ACHPR 1986, CAT, CRC, CEDAW among others.

⁶ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, adopted by General Assembly Resolution 2200A (XXI) of 16 December 1966, entered into force 23 March 1976; International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, adopted and opened for signature, ratification and accession by General Assembly Resolution 2200A (XXI) of 16 December 1966, entered into force 3 January 1976

⁷ Law No. 2008/001 of 14 April 2008 to amend and supplement some provisions of Law No. 96/06 of 18 January 1996 to amend the constitution of 2 June 1972.

⁸ The constitutionalization of human rights is both ancient and recent. Ancient in that it is derived from the French Declaration of the Rights of Man and Citizens of 1789 and recent in that we witness how it grew in the 1990s. Generally, the constitution consecrates human rights and their arrangements or layout is of an infra constitutional order.

Rights, came up with some human rights stipulations as provided in the preamble of the constitution. Although as a general rule, preambles do not form part of State Constitutions, Cameroon provides the exception by upholding the preamble as part and parcel of the constitution by virtue of the provisions of Section 65 of the same constitution⁹.

Prisoners are bestowed with the civil and political as well as the economic, social and cultural rights. These rights are guaranteed in the 1996 constitution of Cameroon without specific distinction but remain singly identified. Nevertheless, both groups of rights remain interrelated, legally protected and indivisible. However, there are no clear provision on the protection of detained persons. Even though it declares that the human person, without distinction as to status, race, religion, sex, or belief possesses inalienable and sacred rights¹⁰.

The 1996 constitution alongside other ratified international treaties all provide for the rights of persons under any form of detention. From a monist perspective and by virtue of article 45 of the same constitution, duly ratified international treaties shall following their promulgation override national laws provided the other party to the treaty apply same. Thus, the constitution and international instruments constitute part of the same law in Cameroon.

In spite of the fact that prisoners' rights enjoy considerable recognition under International Law, it finds a less receptive audience in Cameroon. In line with this, the Cameroon Human Rights Commission¹¹ (CHRC) has consistently reported on the dehumanizing conditions of detention in Cameroon. Annual reports of this commission continue to report that prisons are old and dilapidated, overcrowded, lack food in quantity and quality, not conducive for human accommodation, lack sufficient funding and marred with the spread of communicable diseases like syphilis, malaria, HIV/AIDS, among others¹². The end result is the violation of the rights of prisoners within the prisons. Therefore, this paper seeks to critically discuss the limits of the constitution in protecting

⁹ It provides that 'the Preamble shall form part and parcel of the Cameroon constitution'

¹⁰ This ties with the philosophical approach to human rights conceived by Professor Frans Viljoen who views human rights as those moral claims which human beings possess by virtue of their humanity whereby such rights are inalienable and inherent in the human person.

¹¹ Cameroon Human Rights Commission., Report on the State of Human Rights in Cameroon. (Yaounde: Ets Messie Printers and Publishers, 2025) The National Commission on Human Rights and Freedoms (NCHRF) is an independent, government-funded institution for consultation, monitoring, evaluation, dialogue, concerted action, promotion, and protection of human rights. The Cameroon Human Rights Commission (CHRC) was established by a 1990 presidential decree and subsequently given more powers by a 2004 law. CHRC powers are limited, however. It can only make recommendations to competent authorities. The commission publishes yearly reports on the human rights environment and may engage in research, provide education, coordinate actions with NGOs, and visit prisons and detention sites

¹² H.N Fontebo., Prison Conditions in Cameroon. The Narratives of Female Inmates. Unpublished PhD Thesis, University of South Africa, 2013; Cameroon Human Rights Commission., Report on the State of Human Rights in Cameroon. (Yaounde: Ets Messie Printers and Publishers, 2025); In *Turner v. Safley* [1887] 482, U.S 78, it was held that Prison walls do not form a barrier separating prison inmates from the protections of the Constitution.

prisoners' rights through the spectrum of judicial decisions and state obligations under international human rights law. The methodology adopted in this paper is the qualitative approach which seeks to consult, analyse and interpret both primary and secondary data relevant to the subject. The paper therefore is underpinned by the triple pronged theory of Henry Shue whereby states must respect, protect and fulfil the rights of prisoners under ratified international human rights treaties.

2. THE OBLIGATION TO PROTECT PRISONERS' RIGHTS

States obligations to protect prisoners' rights have been asserted by Henry Shue in his triple pronged theory¹³. He asserted the tripartite analysis of the obligations of States under international human rights instruments. These obligations were affirmed by the Maastricht Guidelines on the Violation of economic, social and cultural rights in 1997. These guidelines represent contemporary statutes of international law.

The theory holds that States are under the obligation to respect, protect and fulfill the rights of its citizens¹⁴. In the context of socio-economic rights, the duty to respect entails that states should not directly infringe the rights of its citizens¹⁵. For instance, by failing to provide citizens with their basic necessities or means for the realization of their basic needs like food, water, education, good health and shelter amounts to a direct infringement of their rights¹⁶. This fits well into the context of this research as detainees rely on the state for the enjoyment of some of their basic rights like the right to good

¹³ H.Shue., *Basic Rights: Subsistence, Affluence and US Foreign Policy*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, (1980); H. Shue., "Basic Rights". *Essays in Philosophy*. (2008), vol. 9, No 2, 1-8 at 6

¹⁴The Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties specifies that States parties are bound by their treaty obligations and all treaty obligations must be performed in good faith (the principle of *pact sunt servanda*). Article 27 of the Vienna Convention reads: "A party may not invoke the provisions of its internal law as justification for its failure to perform a treaty. The right to legal aid in criminal matters is specifically provided in Article 14 of the ICCPR 1966. Article 14(3) "In the determination of any criminal charge against him, everyone shall be entitled to the following minimum guarantees, in full equality: To be tried in his presence, and to defend himself in person or through legal assistance of his own choosing; to be informed, if he does not have legal assistance, of this right; and to have legal assistance assigned to him, in any case where the interests of justice so require, and without payment by him in any such case if he does not have sufficient means to pay for it;" The ICCPR protects not only the rights of those charged with offences: it protects many other rights including the right to life, the right to security of the person and other civil and political rights.

¹⁵G. Tunkin., *Theory of International Law*. London, (1974), p. 81. Tunkin asserts that the content of the principle of respect for human rights in international law may be expressed in three propositions: (1) all states have a duty to respect the fundamental rights and freedoms of all persons within their territories; (2) states have a duty not to permit discrimination by reason of sex, race, religion or language, and (3) states have a duty to promote universal respect for human rights and to co-operate with each other to achieve this objective. In other words, the focus was not upon the individual (as in Western conceptions of human rights) but solely upon the state. Human rights were not directly regulated by international law and individuals were not subjects of international law. Indeed, human rights were implemented by the state and matters basically and crucially within the domestic affairs of the state. He emphasized, 'conventions on human rights do not grant rights directly to individuals.

¹⁶It is an obligation to abstain from taking actions that could violate the rights of detainees. This is a negative obligation that obliges states not to violate human rights and can be contrasted with the obligation to protect and fulfill which are positive obligations.

health, right to fair hearing, the right to a good and conducive standard of living. This is equally supported by the claim that whenever a state deprives somebody of his or her liberty by imprisonment, it also deprives him or her to access outside assistance from friends, family, lawyers and doctors. Accordingly, the State assumes the role of direct and immediate guarantor of the right to life, to good health, and humane treatment for persons in state custody, given that such persons are impeded from satisfying on their own a series of basic necessities that are essential for the development of a dignified life¹⁷.

The duty to protect human rights obliges States to take all legal and institutional measures to ensure that third parties do not infringe on the rights of its citizens¹⁸. The State protects them both from the infringement by the States own instrumentalities and other persons within its jurisdictions. This explains why the state has enacted the Cameroon Penal Code¹⁹ to punish those who violate the rights of citizens through criminal acts. For example, the right to life is protected by criminalizing the crime of murder and capital murder as demonstrated in sections 275²⁰ and 276²¹ of the penal code. The right to property is protected by criminalizing theft; aggravated theft under section 318²² and 320²³ of the penal code and the protection of the right to dignity and prohibition of inhuman, cruel and degrading treatment is by criminalizing the offence of assault on a person by the Penal Code²⁴.

Of evident importance for the wellbeing of prisoners is the obligation on States to protect them against lethal violence and ill treatment by other detainees. Although this positive obligation is not expressly provided for in any of the general human rights instruments, all of them are being interpreted and applied in such a way that they do require the State to afford such protection²⁵.

¹⁷Case of *Children Rehabilitation v. Paraguay* (Panchito Lopez case) 2 September 2004, series C, No.112, paras 205-206.

¹⁸Under article 1 of the African Charter, States assume the obligation to “adopt legislative or other measures to give effect” to the rights protected under that treaty.

¹⁹Law No. 2016/007 of 12 July 2016 enacting the Cameroon Penal Code.

²⁰Whoever causes another’s death shall be punished with imprisonment for life.

²¹Whoever commits murder: after premeditation; or by poisoning; with a view to trafficking the organs of the victim; in the preparation, facilitation or commission of a felony or misdemeanour, or to enable the escape or to procure the impunity of the offender of an accessory to such felony or misdemeanour, shall be punished with death.

²²Whoever causes loss to another: by theft, that is by removing his property; or by misappropriation that is by destruction, waste or conversion of any property capable of being removed entrusted to him for the purpose of custody, return, accounting or any particular manner of dealing; by false pretence, that is by influencing him deceitfully by tricks or by misrepresentation: shall be punished with imprisonment for from 5 to 10 years and with a fine of from 100.000 to 1.000.000FCFA.

²³The penalties provided for in section 318 above shall be doubled if the theft was committed either: with force, or bearing weapons, or by breaking in, by climbing in, or by the use of a false key, or with a motor vehicle; whoever commits a theft by the use of force causing the death of another or grievous harm as provided in section 277 and 279 of the penal code shall be punished with death.

²⁴Section 277 of the Penal code.

²⁵In cases of massive killings, the African Commission has recognized a State duty under the African Charter to protect the life and safety of all citizens against violence and damaging acts by non-state actors. Since the duty applies to all citizens, it should include the obligation to protect detainees against violence by

The UN Covenant on Civil and Political Rights contains several provisions that have been used by the Human Rights Committee to formulate State obligations to protect prisoners against each other as well as against themselves. Especially relevant are article 6 (1), which demands that the right to life 'shall be protected by law', and article 10(1), which stipulates that 'All persons deprived of their liberty shall be treated with humanity and with respect for the inherent dignity of the human person'. In the case of *Barbato v. Uruguay*²⁶, the Human Rights Committee recognizes that the right to life implies that the state has a duty to take adequate measures to protect the life of a prisoner against suicide, forced suicide and killing by others while in custody. And in the case of *Daley v. Jamaica*²⁷ the State's neglect to take measures to protect the complainant, who was assaulted regularly by other inmates, was one of the main factors that led the Committee to conclude that article 10 (1) ICCPR had been breached. The justification of this duty to protect prisoners is apparently that they are particularly vulnerable because of their status as persons deprived of liberty and that the State party, by arresting and detaining individuals, takes on the responsibility to care for their life, wellbeing, and, presumably, the dignity of the person. To avoid such violations against them it is at least incumbent on the State to resolve problems of prison overcrowding and to segregate different categories of detainees.

The duty to fulfill requires that states should take positive measures towards the realization of the rights of its citizens. These measures can be administrative, financial and legislative as well as in the form of policy initiatives, monitoring and education. That is, the making available of adequate funds to the prison sector is a measure to fulfill the rights of detainees. Fulfillment implicitly will imply the availability, accessibility, adequacy and provision of quality goods and services to citizens.

Hence, the triple pronged theory provides a gate way to investigate Cameroon's engagement to respect, protect and fulfill the rights of detainees as provided in international law. The United Nations Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights has developed a number of indicators for assessing compliance with this aspect of state obligations.

In Cameroon, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) remains the core international human rights treaty on the protection of the rights of prisoners. Cameroon has ratified the Covenant and is bound to incorporate its provisions into domestic law and state practice. The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESR) states that everyone should have a right for getting the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health prisoners inclusive. Also, the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners, 1955 consisting of five parts and ninety-five rules.

Part one providing the rules for the general applications. It declares that there would be no discrimination on grounds of race, colour, sex, the languages, religions,

other prisoners. Furthermore, this would be in keeping with the principle that the State's responsibility for someone's integrity and wellbeing 'is heightened in cases where an individual is in its custody'. This principle is explained by the complete dependence of prisoners on the actions of the authorities. The right to 'life and the integrity of his person' in article 4, the prohibition of 'torture, cruel, inhuman or degrading punishment and treatment' in article 5, and 'the right to liberty and to the security of his person' in article 6 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights (ACHPR) (can) in particular serve as a basis for the obligation.

²⁶HRC, View of 21 October 1982, Comm. 84/1981, para 9.2 and 10(a).

²⁷ HRC, View of 31 July 1998, Comm. 750/1997, para 76.

political views or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or any other status. At the same time, it is strongly need of respecting the others' religious belief and moral precepts of the group to which the prisoners belong. The standard rule respects the consideration to the separation of the different categories of prisoners. It is indicating that the men and women must be detained in separate institutions. The under- trial prisoners must have to keep separate from the convicted prisoners. Further, it advocates the complete separations between the prisoners detained under civil law and the criminal offences made by them. The UN standard Minimum Rule states that, it is mandatory to provide the separate residence for young and child prisoners from the adult prisoners. Subsequent UN directives have been the Basic Principles for the Treatment of Prisoners (United Nations 1990) and the Body of Principles for the Protection of All Persons under Any Form of Detention or Imprisonment (United Nations 1988).

For the issues of the prison offences and punishment, standard minimum rules are very clear. These rules state that “no prisoner should be punished unless he/she has been informed of the offences alleged against him or her and given a proper opportunity of presenting his or her defence”. It recommends that the corporal punishment placing in a dark cell and all “cruel, in-human or degrading punishments should completely be prohibited as the mode of punishments and disciplinary actions” in the prisons.

3. THE RIGHTS OF PRISONERS IN CAMEROON

All persons shall have equal rights and obligations before the law²⁸. The state shall provide all its citizens with the conditions necessary for their development. This right is the corner stone, the bedrock of all human rights principles. This is because it focuses on the fact that people should enjoy or be treated as equal, mindless of their sex, status, religion, race nor language.²⁹ This cardinal principle is contained in the United States Constitution as in Cameroon³⁰. In the case of *City of Cleburne, Texas v. Cleburne Living Center*³¹, it was held that to prevail on an equal protection claim, a detainee must prove the following two instances of discrimination: firstly, that the State treated him or her differently from others who were similarly situated; and that the difference in treatment was not rationally related to any legitimate governmental interest³².

²⁸Pursuant to the principle of equality of all citizens before the law, judicial institutions function without any discrimination. In principle, all citizens have equal access to justice. Hence, Article 6(1) of Ordinance No. 72/4 of 1972 to organize the judiciary states that, justice shall be free except for fiscal provisions relating to stamp duty and registration

²⁹As earlier stated in chapter one of this thesis, natural law philosophers like Aristotle and John Locke holds the view that equality is a natural right that must be respected and recognized by all persons given that it is inherent and inalienable. Nevertheless, their view has been subjected to opposition especially the view of Sandra Fredman who believes that in nature, there is the principle of rule and subordination in nature at large, hence, human beings by their very nature are bound to discriminate.

³⁰U.S. Constitution. amendment. XIV, (1). It embodies equality of courts, fair and public hearing, by competent, independent and impartial tribunal established by law, right to compensation in cases of miscarriage of justice, and the prohibition of double jeopardy.

³¹ (1985) 473 U.S. 432, 439

³²See *Village of Willowbrook v. Olech*. (2000) 528 U.S. 562, 564; In the celebrated case of *President of the Republic of South Africa v Hugo* (1997 (4) SA 1 CC. In 1994 the President granted a special remission of sentence to all mothers in prison at the time who had children under the age of 12 years. The respondent,

Furthermore, No person may be prosecuted, arrested or detained except in the cases and according to the manner determined by law³³. This provision is also provided in the Ethiopian constitution³⁴ in that no Ethiopian subject may be arrested, sentenced, or imprisoned except in pursuance of the law. This provision, however, does not have clear provision on treatment of detained persons in Cameroon and Ehtiopia. As such cannot effectively protect detainees rights to fair hearing, arrest and detention.

Similarly, the law shall ensure the right of every one to a fair hearing before the courts³⁵. This is an inalienable right found in Article 10 of the UDHR, which states that “everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him. Further, Article 7(1)(d) of the ACHPR specifies that the individual right to have one’s cause heard includes “the right to be tried within a reasonable time by an impartial court or tribunal[³⁶].” Detainees in the Yaounde, Douala, Buea and Bamenda central prisons are being held beyond the statutorily defined time limits[³⁷] for custody without bail, constituting a clear violation of their right to have their case adjudicated ‘within a reasonable time.’

In *The State Prosecutor v. Ngum Ngwane*³⁸, the accused was arrested and detained in Mundemba. He was later transfered to the Buea Central Prison and charged with terrorism by the Military Tribunal in Buea, charges which he pleaded not guilty. He was therefore remanded in custody since 2018. Surprisingly, as of September 2019, his case has not been heard for reasons of non-composition of the court. This is a violation of

a prisoner, who was the father of a child under twelve, challenged the presidential order arguing that it unfairly discriminated against him on the grounds of sex or gender. The majority of the court held that although this was discrimination, it was not unfair. In a dissenting judgment, Mokgoro J held that the measure amounted to unfair discrimination, but justified it under the limitation clause. This case illustrates two important points. First that a distinction has to be made between fair and unfair discrimination. Only unfair discrimination is outlawed. Secondly, prisoners' rights, indeed all rights, are not absolute. They are subject to certain limitations.

³³International human rights law instruments like the UDHR, ICCPR, UNSMR, provides that where a state practices detention, it must not be arbitrary and must be on grounds established by law.it must be subject to prompt and effective judicial control, at least on the initiative of the detainee, the detainee must be informed of the reasons behind his detention, of the right to communicate. Such detention must not be incommunicado for more than a few days, and the detainee must be registered. Also, such detention must not be discriminatory, it must be humane with access to regular medical evaluation and treatment. Equally, the detainee must be compensated in cases where his or her detention turns out to be unlawful

³⁴ Constitution of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia, Federal Negarit Gazetta, Proclamation No. 1/ 1995.

³⁵ In Cameroon, the right to fair hearing must be respected in all courts be it ordinary courts, or courts with special jurisdiction. This right was first exercised by God following the events that happened in the Garden of Eden between Adam and Eve. When Adam and Eve ate the fruit from the tree, he had asked them not to eat, God did not just punish them. He went ahead to asked Adam why he ate the fruit and Adam replied by saying that the woman you gave to me tricked me to eat. To exercised fair hearing, he went further to ask Eve why she had to eat the fruit from the tree he had prohibited them not to eat and Eve replied by stating that the snaked tricked me to eat the fruit. Having heard both parties, God therefore went ahead to declare their punishment. This is a Biblical conceptualization of the right to fair hearing for scholars who believe in Christianity.

³⁸*Military Court Buea*, (2019)

the constitutional right to fair trial as provided for under the preamble of the Cameroon constitution. This systemic shortcoming is worsened by the inaction of members of the prison administration. Specifically, interviewed detainees claim that they are indigent and, therefore, not afforded the opportunity to make phone calls, to contact or procure legal services, or even acquire transportation to their hearing. Moreover, many of the detainees indicated that not only were they not informed of when their court date occurred, they did not even know the reason for their imprisonment³⁹.

In *The People of Cameroon v. Njika Florentine and 5ors*⁴⁰, the matter was dismissed based on provisions of section 3 of the CPC for violating the need for diligent and speedy prosecution as a requirement for fair hearing. Together, these procedural deficiencies amount to a gross violation of the rights of accused detainees to a fair hearing. In *Southern Cameroon National Congress v. Cameroon*⁴¹, the right to a fair hearing was violated following the arrest of Southern Cameroonians who were caught and detained for a pretty long time without trial. This equally violated the cardinal principle of international law requiring people facing the arm of the law to be tried promptly or within a reasonable time. In *R v. University of Cambridge*⁴², Fortescue J linked the concept of fair hearing to natural law and natural justice. He issued a writ of *mandamus* to the University of Cambridge requiring the institution to restore to one Dr. Bentley his degrees of Bachelor of arts and Doctor of Divinity of which he had been deprived of by the university without a hearing.

The case of *Ex Parte Hull*⁴³ is considered to be the genesis of prisoners' access to courts in the United States. In *Hull*, the Supreme Court struck down a Michigan statute that prohibited prisoners from filing legal documents with the courts unless they were found to be "properly drawn" by the parole board, saying "the State and its officers may not abridge or impair petitioner's right to apply to a federal court for a writ of Habeas Corpus. In later cases, the Supreme Court struck down other obstacles such as economic barriers⁴⁴. Moreover, in *Johnson v. Avery*⁴⁵, the Supreme Court also struck down a Tennessee regulation which prohibited inmates from assisting each other in preparation of Habeas Corpus petitions unless the state provided a reasonable alternative of petitions for post conviction relief. In *Legal Practitioner Disciplinary Committee v. Fawehinmi*⁴⁶, it was held that even an administrative tribunal is bound to observe the right to fairhearing that govern the exercise of judicial functions.

³⁹See also *The Prosecutor v. Apane Brandon* (2019) (Military Tribunal Buea).

⁴⁰Suit No. CFIB/O11c/2006.

⁴¹(2004) African Human Rights Law Report (AHRLR), 43.

⁴²(1723) 93 ER 698.

⁴³This judgement was followed in subsequent cases like *Cooper v. Board of Works* (1863)143 ER 414; *University of Ceylon v. Fernando* (1960) 1 WLR 223.

⁴⁴See *Griffin v. Illinois*, 351 U.S. 12 (1956) (fee for trial transcript necessary for appellate review was unfairly burdensome on indigent prisoners); *Burns v. Ohio*, 360 U.S. 252 (1959) (requiring States to waive filing fees for indigent prisoners).

⁴⁵(1969) 393 U.S. 483

⁴⁶(1985) 2 WLR 300.

However, access to court as a prerequisite of the right to fair hearing remains a problem to most detainees in Cameroon. In *The People v. Justice Nyoh Wakai and 172 Ors*⁴⁷, Justice Fombe ordered the immediate release of the detainees who were detained successively by different administrative authorities for a continuous period of four months without hearing .

A prerequisite to the fulfilment of the right to fair hearing is the need for detainees to be prosecuted in public. However, the requirement for public trial especially in criminal cases was violated by the court of first instance Buea in *The people v. Roland Minang*⁴⁸ and that of *The People v. Sigalla Rene and co*⁴⁹. During the hearing of these cases, access by the public was curtailed for reasons unknown to the public. Entrances to the court were all blocked by Gendarmes and the Police officers and lawyers could only access courts by presentation of professional cards. This was the view of the United Nations Human Rights Committee in *Womah Mukong v. Cameroon*⁵⁰, whereby the committee held that cameroon laws inhibit the right to access courts.

Equally, every accused person is presumed innocent until found guilty during a hearing conducted in strict compliance with the rights of the defence. Upholding this cardinal principle of criminal law and constitutional rule Lonneken Stevens⁵¹ finds that to detain a suspect is to deprive him from his liberty without having a judge establish his guilt within a fair trial. A pre-trial detainee may turn out to be innocent in the end. Therefore, when pre-trial detention is perceived to be applied too easily, too often, or too long, it is alleged that pre-trial detention practice should be more in keeping with the presumption of innocence. The presumption requires that the state treats the suspect as if he were innocent.

In *CDC v. Isa Bongam*⁵², the South West Court of Appeal held that the right to fair hearing is a legal principle of natural justice which holds that no one shall be condemned unheard and requires those who handle disputes between parties to act fairly in good faith, without bias and in judicial temperament. Nevertheless, this is a normative rather than a factual assumption. Ashworth⁵³ supports Lonneke's idea by arguing that the presumption of innocence is a moral and political principle, based on a widely shared conception of how a free society should exercise the power to punish. The relevance of this principle in the preamble of the Cameroon constitution is to protect a detainee against arbitrary and excessive state action.

More over, every person has the right to life, to physical and moral integrity and to humane treatment in all circumstances. Under no circumstances shall any person be

⁴⁷ (1997) 1 CCLR 127-254.

⁴⁸ Suit No. CFIB/13C/2012 (Unreported).

⁴⁹ Suit No. CFIB/24C/2012 (Unreported).

⁵⁰ Communication No. 458/1991, UN DOC.CCPR/C/51/D/458/1991.

⁵¹ S. Lonneke., "Pre-Trial Detention: The Presumption of Innocence and Article 5 of the European Convention on Human Rights Cannot and Does Not Limit its Increasing Use". *European Journal of Crime, Criminal Law and Criminal Justice*, (2009) 17 165-180 at 167.

⁵² (1997) 1CCLR, P.261

⁵³ A. Ashworth., "Four Threats to the Presumption of Innocence". *International Journal of Evidence and Proof*. (2006) 10, 249.

subjected to torture, to cruel, inhumane or degrading treatment⁵⁴. As such, the practice of putting detainees in chains when bringing them to court or as punishment for committing an offence in the prison facility is viewed as inhuman and degrading. This explains why sections 347 of the Criminal Procedure code in support of the constitutional provisions prohibits the practice by holding that detainees who are detained shall be brought unfettered before the court.

This guarantee is also protected in various international Instruments that have been incorporated into Cameroonian law by the constitution: the UN Charter Articles 55 and 56 and UDHR Article 3 each state that “everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person.” Article 5(b) of the International Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Racial Discrimination and Article 6 of the ICCPR equally protect the right to life, physical and moral integrity, while Article 4 of the ACHPR states that “human beings are inviolable. Every human being shall be entitled to respect for his life and the integrity of his person. No one shall be arbitrarily deprived of this right.” The freedom from torture is also protected by Article 7 of the ICCPR, which states that: “no one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment. In particular, no one shall be subjected without his free consent to medical or scientific experimentation”.

However, the strongest protection is found in the Convention on Torture or Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Punishment or Treatment of 1984 (CAT). Article 1(1) defines torture as: “...any act by which severe pain or suffering, whether physical or mental, is intentionally inflicted on a person for such purposes as obtaining from him or a third person information or a confession, punishing him for an act he or a third person has committed or is suspected of having committed, or intimidating or coercing him or a third person, or for any reason based on discrimination of any kind, when such pain or suffering is inflicted by or at the instigation of or with the consent or acquiescence of a public official or other person acting in an official capacity. It does not include pain or suffering arising only from, inherent in or incidental to lawful sanctions.”

As this definition indicates, there are several elements to the concept of torture:

- (1) severe pain or suffering, which can be physical or mental;
- (2) that it is intentionally inflicted;
- (3) for a specific purpose such as punishment;

⁵⁴ In *Conjwayo v. Minister of Justice, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs and Others* (1992) (2) SA 56, the applicant challenged the conditions of detention. The prisoner who was under sentence of death, was confined in a small single cell for a minimum of 23 hours every weekday and 24 hours on Saturdays, Sundays and public holidays, without access to natural light and fresh air, and with only limited ability to exercise his body. He argued that such conditions infringed his fundamental right under section 15(1) of the Constitution of Zimbabwe not to be subjected to inhuman treatment. Accepting that it had a responsibility to enforce the constitutional rights of all persons, prisoners included, the court held that indeed such conditions of detention infringed the prisoners' fundamental rights. To subject a human being to such conditions, the court further held, transgressed the boundaries of civilized standards and involved the infliction of unnecessary suffering. The court ordered that the applicant be allowed to exercise in the open air, every weekday, for one hour in the morning and one hour in the afternoon, and on weekends and public holidays for a minimum of one hour a day.

(4) by the order, or with the consent, of a public official.

The welding of chains on to the arms and legs of the 23 awaiting trial detainees on August 28th of 2018 for crimes committed in detention constitutes an act of torture under the CAT definition. First, the testimony of the detainees as to the pain experienced both during and after the ordeal, and as a result of the subsequent beatings, along with visual confirmation of the severe scarring by the researcher, indicates that each of the victims experienced extreme physical suffering. Second, the act was intentionally inflicted, as evidenced by prison authority's summoning of an unidentified welder to the prison specifically for the purpose of welding the shackles onto the detainees. Third, the act was clearly intended as a punishment for the detainees strike against the poor conditions at the Douala Central Prison. Finally, the act was perpetrated by the order of the prison's superintendent. As all of the definitional elements are satisfied, it is clear that the August 18 actions by the prison authority amount to an act of torture.

The state shall guarantee the child's right to education. The relevance of this right is heightened by the fact that it constituted one of the Millennium Development Goals (MDG) which is now Sustainable Development Goals (SDG). It provides for the universal realisation of literacy through compulsory primary or elementary education. This however is not meant for only free citizens or those who enjoy their liberty but applies to detainees, especially juveniles. It is a cardinal principle of international human rights law that the practice of detention must not be carried out in such a manner that it destroys the life projects of a child.

Nevertheless, even though Cameroon has actually achieved the right to universal education through free elementary education, it is not however compulsory as a child under prison custody does not have this chance to attend elementary education. This applies also to children who come from poor background, independent of the fact that they enjoy their liberty. Thus, the realization of the right to compulsory elementary education must be adopted in prison administration. This reform can move from informal education to formal education as the latter is practiced in the prison milieu to an extent as not all detainees have the opportunity to participate.

There are several benefits for detainees to acquire compulsory universal primary education. The resulting impact spans from realization of the SDG, awareness on health standards and care, struggle to advocate for respect and improvement of detention conditions and facilitates reintegration of the detainee back into the society where he comes from.

These rights are general rights of Cameroonians without any distinction as to race, status, colour, nor religion or nationality and so apply to detainees as Cameroonians. However, detainees rights have been accorded specific recognition in constitutions of some states the world over. But this is not the case in Cameroon. In the Ecuador constitution, article 35 of the constitution provides that elderly persons, girls, children and adolescents, pregnant women, persons with disabilities, persons in prisons and those who suffer disastrous or highly complex diseases shall receive priority and specialized

care in the public and private sectors. The constitutions of Egypt and Ethiopia provide for an omnibus provision requiring the preservation of the human dignity of detained persons⁵⁵. In strong terms, the Togolese constitution⁵⁶ provides that every person who is detained shall nonetheless be treated in a manner that preserves the dignity and physical and mental well-being which shall help with his re-admittance to society. This is highly applauded as it does not only contemplate the detained persons' rights during and after trial but his or her post trial rights upon release. Rights that are not contemplated by the constitution of Cameroon.

Nevertheless, to add force to the rights provided in the preamble of the constitution, article 1, paragraph 3 of the same constitution upholds the need for recognition of general human rights by stating that 'the State shall ensure the equality of all citizens before the law'. This is very relevant to the protection of detained persons' rights as the concept of equality and non discrimination form the backbone to enjoy and have other human rights protected.

4. PRISONS AND CONDITIONS OF DETENTION IN CAMEROON

Conditions of detention in Cameroon remain critical, characterized by severe overcrowding, food shortages, inadequate sanitation, and systemic corruption. With the prison population often exceeding official capacity by 50% or more, inmates face life-threatening environments where access to medical care and basic human rights are heavily compromised.

Severe overpopulation plagues most facilities, including major centers like Yaoundé Central Prison and Douala's New Bell. Many of the country's prison facilities lack adequate sleeping space, ventilation, and sanitation. Accommodation⁵⁷ is one of the

⁵⁵ Article 42 of the Egyptian Constitution of 2014 and Article 21 of the Ethiopian Constitution of 1995.

⁵⁶ Article 16 of the Constitution of Togo of 1992 as amended in 2007. It provides that every accused person or detained [person] must benefit from a treatment that preserves their dignity, their physical and mental health and that aids their social rehabilitation. No one has the right to obstruct an accused person or detained [person] from being examined by a doctor of their choice. Every accused [person] has the right to be assisted by counsel at the stage of the preliminary inquiry. Article 17 and 18 of the same constitution provides for detainees' rights to be presumed innocent until proven guilty, while article 19 provides for the right to a fair trial.

⁵⁷ Article 16 of the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment provides: Each State Party shall undertake to prevent in any territory under its jurisdiction other acts of cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment which do not amount to torture ... when such acts are committed by or at the instigation of or with the consent or acquiescence of a public official or other person acting in an official capacity. ... The Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners require as follows: (1) Where sleeping accommodation is in individual cells or rooms, each prisoner shall occupy by night a cell or room by himself. ... (2) Where dormitories are used, they shall be occupied by prisoners carefully selected as being suitable to associate with one another in those conditions. There shall be regular supervision by night, in keeping with the nature of the institution. All accommodation provided for the use of prisoners and in particular all sleeping accommodation shall meet all requirements of health, due regard being paid to climatic conditions and particularly to cubic content of air, minimum floor space, lighting, heating and ventilation. In all places where prisoners are required to live or work, (a) The windows shall be large enough to enable the prisoners to read or work by natural light, and shall be so constructed that they can allow the entrance of fresh air whether or not

basic needs for human survival. The ICESCR in article 11 provides for the right of everyone to an adequate standard of living for himself and his family, including adequate food, clothing and housing. As a prerequisite, specifically, article 10 of the ICCPR provides that detained persons must be treated with respect for their inherent human dignity. The UN Standard Minimum Rules for Treatment of Prisoners points out the minimum level of provision of accommodation stating that:

... the sleeping accommodation shall meet all requirements of health, due regard being paid to climatic conditions and particularly to cubic content of air, minimum floor space, lighting, heating and ventilation.

Cameroon has ratified the aforementioned instruments and is hereby bound by the obligations⁵⁸. Moreover, detained persons are guaranteed with similar legal protection in Cameroonian legislations. While the preamble of the constitution stipulates in general terms without specific mention of detainees or any category of people provides that ‘all persons have the right to good standard of living’. This imply that persons held in custody and persons imprisoned upon conviction and sentencing have the right to treatments concerning their human dignity and failure of the state to provide adequate accommodation to detainees, violates their rights to good standard of living, dignity and accommodation.

Review of literature ranging from institutional reports and academic circles have persistently identified accommodation as a major problem in Cameroon prisons. In this regard, the National Commission for Human Rights and Freedoms in its 2017 annual report asserts that most prisons in Cameroon remain overcrowded and dilapidated. This problem runs through all the reports of this commission. On similar basis, a 2002 report by the Special Rapporteur on Prisons in Africa⁵⁹, during her visit to Cameroon, identified the problem of accommodation caused by overcrowding. Several recommendations were made by this body for measures to be taken to ensure that detainees are accommodated under hygienic and decent conditions. Nevertheless, 19 years later, the problem of accommodation is worsening. As such, recommendations by the Human Rights Commission and the Special Rapporteur on prisons remain a paper work and lack the

there is artificial ventilation; (b) Artificial light shall be provided sufficient for the prisoners to read or work without injury to eyesight. ... The medical officer shall regularly inspect and advise the director upon: ... (c) The sanitation, heating, lighting and ventilation of the institution; The Guidelines and Measures for the Prohibition and Prevention of Torture, Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment in Africa (The Robben Island Guidelines) provides that States should: Take steps to improve conditions in places of detention which do not conform to international standards.

⁵⁸ See the triple pronged theory in chapter one above (obligations to respect, protect and fulfill human rights)

⁵⁹ The accommodation condition of prisons in Cameroon is addressed by the Special Rapporteur on Prisons to African, Mission to Cameroon. The report pointed out that all the detention facilities visited, including the police stations, are overcrowded, some holding inmates more than twice their capacity. The overcrowding is attributed to the large number of un-sentenced prisoners. Specifically, in the Yaounde Central Prison, more than 3242 out of the over 4835 inmates, about 68% of the total inmate population have not been sentenced. In all the prisons, there are no separate areas for inmates to store their belongings. Prisoners have therefore resorted to making holes on the walls to hang their things. This makes most of the cells very crowded, dark and less airy.

force of implementation. This view has been upheld by some academic scholars like Helen Fontebo⁶⁰.

Accommodation remains a pertinent problem plaguing Cameroonian prisons.⁶¹ In *Albert Mukong v. Cameroon*⁶², some minimum conditions for detainees such as floor space, cubic content of air for each prisoner, adequate sanitary facilities, clothing and food in concert with the UNSMR for the treatment of prisoners were complied with. The committee on human rights in Africa stressed that minimum requirements should always be observed regardless of economic constraints suffered by the state. Noncompliance with minimum standards amounted to a violation of article 10(1) and in particular any harsh treatment that the victim was subjected to such as incommunicado detention and threats of torture, equally amounted to a violation of article 7 of the ICCPR 1966.

The situation in the Buea and Bamenda Central Prisons has been worsened following the advent of the Anglophone crisis. The Chief of Service in-charge of Discipline at the Buea central prison asserts that:

Accommodation has always been a major problem to detainees in Cameroon and this has been further complicated by the massive arrest and detention of people during the Anglophone crisis. The Buea central prison housed over 800 detainees before the Anglophone crisis started in 2016. As of December 2018, the prison has a total population of over 1300 detainees after the release of over 90 that benefited from the presidential pardon. A single cell now houses over 100 detainees which is inhuman and degrading. The increase in prison population is not followed by budgetary allocations and no new cells are being constructed.⁶³

Boh and Ofege⁶⁴ describe Kondengui as a prison where “inmates wake up to line up behind each other and take turns urinating on the little mountain of faeces in one corner of the cell, chipping it off and scattering the pieces onto the floor”. Tande paints a picture of Kondengui prison as a microcosm of the prison conditions in Cameroon. According to Tande, Kondengui prison is defined as “hell on earth”⁶⁵.

⁶⁰ H.N Fontebo, op cit footnote 447

⁶¹ P.I.Bah., *Beyond the Prison Gates: Deep Spiritual Reflections from the Prison*. (Douala: 2017).

⁶² Communication No. 458/1991

⁶³ Researcher field work, Buea Central Prison, 20/04/ 2026.

⁶⁴ Boh and Ofege in H.N Fontebo., *Prison Conditions in Cameroon: the narratives of female inmates*. PhD Thesis, University of South Africa, 2013. P. 114.

⁶⁵ D. Tande., *An overview of Cameroon prison literature from Albert Mukong to Titus Edzoa* (2012). Accessed online 21 January 2019; Kondengui prison was constructed for 800 people but sometimes it houses 4500 inmates. Tande describes the responses of the participants in his study thus: I was sleeping on a little bed of 40cm wide and 180cm long in a room of 4mx4 [sic]. They could say we were in the VIP

As regard accommodation in the Yaounde Central prison, the chief of service In-charge of socio-cultural activities states thus:

Accommodation is a major problem in the prison due to the daily increase in number of detainees. The capacity of this prison is 1500 but as of now, the prison has 4567 detainees comprising those awaiting trial and those that have been sentenced. This causes serious shortage of cells, beds, and other needed service. As such, some detainees sleep out of the cells and on bare floor. It has led to health problems and other negative vices. This problem does not only violate detainees' rights but poses serious security and control problems within the prison.⁶⁶

A large portion of the prison population often estimated between 60% and 75% consists of pre-trial detainees. Many faces prolonged detentions without formal charges, often driven by endemic corruption and case mismanagement.

Inmates, including juveniles and those sentenced to death, are frequently held in the same wards as condemned adult offenders. The co-habitation of vulnerable groups exacerbates risks of abuse and neglect. For those facing the death penalty, conditions are notoriously harsh, with inmates suffering from severe abandonment and lack of targeted medical or psychiatric care.

Food insufficiency and poor nutritional quality are chronic problems. Malnutrition and the rapid spread of communicable diseases are significant health risks due to the poor state of facilities and limited medical staffing. Article 11 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights ensures the right to adequate food as a component of the right of everyone to an adequate standard of living. Article 11, paragraph 2, specifically provides that States parties recognize the fundamental right of everyone to be free from hunger. The right to adequate food is further developed by the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights in its General Comment No. 12 (1999) on the subject, which provides: The right to adequate food is realized when every man, woman and child, alone or in community with others, has physical and economic access at all times to adequate food or means for its procurement. The right to adequate food shall therefore not be interpreted in a narrow or restrictive sense which equates it with a minimum package of calories, proteins and other specific nutrients. ... The Committee considers that the core content of the right to adequate food implies:

quarters because we could afford our food and could arrange for our quarter to be cleaned. But, what about the others? If you go to Kondengui you would hear of Kosovo. In Kondengui prison it is possible to find approximately 1300 people in small quarters. A room that is supposed to take a maximum of 20 people will be packed with 80 inmates, with three people lying on a little bed 40 centimetres wide.

⁶⁶ Researcher field work Yaounde Central prison, interview of the Chief of service incharge of Sociocultural activities, 9-10th April, 2026.

- (a) The availability of food in a quantity and quality sufficient to satisfy the dietary needs of individuals, free from adverse substances, and acceptable within a given culture;
- (b) The accessibility of such food in ways that are sustainable and that do not interfere with the enjoyment of other human rights⁶⁷.

Water is one of the most valued gifts of nature that mankind would cease to exist in case of its absence. This water must be of good quality. That is, have no colour, no smell, and no taste; it must be pure and capable of human consumption. Otherwise, it shall fail to meet the standards for good drinking water. The importance of water cannot be over emphasized as it is used for drinking, cooking, agriculture and for the generation of energy. This water must be readily available to all without any discrimination. This is backed by the preamble of the Cameroon Constitution of 1996 which provides for good standard of living and the attainment of the right to health care. Lack of good drinking water has serious repercussions, not only on detainees but on the entire society. Equally, article 29 of the 1992 decree on prison administration and reform in Cameroon provides for feeding and the provision of portable water for persons in detention.

But Cameroon prisons fall short of this commodity as there is no ready supply of water for those in detention. At the Yaounde Central Prison, over 4500 are subjected to use one tap and this is worsened by the fact that there is no regular flow of water. As such, detainees go for over a week without water neither to bath nor to keep their cloths clean as required by the UNSMR. Most times, when the water flows, it does not meet the qualities of good drinking water as identified above. In such situations, detainees have no choice to drinking the water. This has contributed to the spread of communicable diseases like cholera in the prison and other water borne diseases.⁶⁸

This raises questions as to Cameroon's obligation to respect, protect and fulfill the rights of detainees⁶⁹. Failure to provide food and water of good quality contravenes article 11 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966) and article 20(2)⁷⁰ of the UNSMR (1955). These require Cameroon to provide detainees with sufficient and healthy food and that drinking water shall be available to every prisoner whenever he needs it⁷¹. The researcher's personal observation and interview of detainees reveal that at the Buea central prison, the most common food is raw banana and each detainee is given 2 or 3 to roast. In addition to it corn and beans is of such small quantity

⁶⁷ Official Records of the Economic and Social Council, 2000, Supplement No. 2 and corrigendum (E/2000/22 and Corr.1), annex V.

⁶⁸ Researcher Field work, Yaounde Central Prison, December 2026.

⁶⁹ Using the triple pronged theory to show how states can meet their obligation to provide water to detainees, the duty to respect imply that Cameroon must not disconnect services of safe water for human consumption and production that is used for the livelihood of detainees; the duty to protect mean that where water services are contaminated by private sector , Cameroon must ensure actions against them and lastly the duty to fulfill imply that Cameroon must take steps to ensure that all detainees are progressively connected to a safe drinking water supply

⁷⁰ Drinking water shall be available to every prisoner whenever he needs it.

⁷¹ As per article 26 of the geneva convention relative to the treatment of prisoners, The basic daily food rations shall be sufficient in quantity, quality and variety to keep prisoners of war in good health and to prevent loss of weight or the development of nutritional deficiencies. Account shall also be taken of the habitual diet of the prisoners.

that even a child of 10 years cannot be full. Food is provided twice a day but it lacks the requisite elements of good quality food.⁷²

At the Yaounde Central Prison, an interview of the chief in charge of discipline and some inmates of the prison revealed that detainees feed once a day in the prison as against 3 meals per day which is provided by the Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners 1955. The common food in the prison includes rice with groundnut soup, rice with beans, corn and beans. The meals were described to be of very low quality and quantity. Nevertheless, on special occasions like the visit of NGOs, detainees eat food provided by such NGOs which is of good quality and quantity. The major hindrance to effectively comply with detainees' right to adequate feeding is the lack of sufficient funds.⁷³

The National Commission on Human Rights and Freedoms shares a similar view on the inmate problem to adequate feeding. In its 2017 report on the state of human rights in Cameroon, this commission noted that despite a slight increase on the feeding budget for detainees from 2016 to 2017, which went from 2,570,000,000 FCFA (250 FCFA per detainee per day) to 3,070,000,000 FCFA in 2017 (273 FCFA per inmate per day), the increase was not reflected in terms of improvement of the quality and quantity of food.⁷⁴

International and local human rights groups continue to document cases of police brutality, torture, and incommunicado detention, particularly in regions affected by separatist conflicts or during periods of political tension.

5. LEGAL FRAMEWORK PROTECTING PRISONERS' RIGHTS IN CAMEROON

Cameroon manifests express and implied intention to protect the rights of prisoners. Alongside the ratification of international treaties protecting these rights, there are constitutional and other legislative mechanisms to protect the rights of prisoners in Cameroon. This will be express in article 45 of the constitution which gives place for international treaties ratified by Cameroon to be directly applicable and shall take precedence in case of any clash with national law. Thus, article 5 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948 provides that no one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman and degrading treatment or punishment. On similar bases, article 9 of the UDHR further states that no one shall be arbitrarily arrested nor detained. These rights are recognized under the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights 1966 (ICCPR 1966)⁷⁵ and thus states are under the tripartite obligation to ensure that prisoners enjoy their rights. On similar grounds, article 6 of the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child recognizes the need not to torture nor subject prisoners under

⁷² Field observation, Buea Central Prison, 20/04/ 2026.

⁷³ Researcher Interview with Chief of Service in charge of Discipline in the Yaounde Central prison and Some inmates of the Prison on 9-10 April, 2026.

⁷⁴ National Commission on Human Rights and Freedom, Report on the State of Human Rights in Cameroon 2017. Yaounde, ets messie printers. Page 91.

⁷⁵ Article 7 and 10 (1) (2), ICCPR 1966

inhuman, cruel or degrading treatment. The convention against torture as well as the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules (UNSMR now Mandela Rules) on similar terms prohibit acts of torture on prisoners.

The normative framework for the protection of prisoners' rights in Cameroon stems from the preamble to the 1996 constitution of Cameroon. In implied terms, this constitution, for the first time in the history of Cameroon Human Rights, came up with some human rights stipulations as provided in the preamble of the constitution. Although as a general rule, preambles do not form part of State Constitutions, Cameroon provides the exception by upholding the preamble as part and parcel of the constitution by virtue of the provisions of Section 65 of the same constitution. Thus, it provide for the right not to be tortured, treated in a cruel, inhuman and degrading way; the right to be given a fair trial within a reasonable time; the right not to be arbitrarily detained as well as the right to good living conditions. Thus. Prisoners like any other citizen can invoke the provisions of the preamble to ensure the respect of his or her rights. The preamble lists these rights without precision and as such the preamble apply to all without distinction as to sex, status, colour, race, religion, nationality or origin.

Similarly, the penal code (2016) is one of the laws regulating the state of human rights in prison and Cameroon in general. Although its scope is defined in terms of prescribing penalties for offences committed within the territory of Cameroon, it provides a convenient atmosphere to promote respect for human rights. Section 24 of the Code provides that imprisonment shall mean the loss of liberty during which the offender shall be obliged to work. This is to fulfil the prisoners fund provided for in section 25 of the penal code. Other sections of the penal code provides for community sentence (section 26); commencement of sentences (section 27 and 28) as well as section 29 of the code which warrants that minors under 18 years should serve their sentences in a special establishment or failing such establishment, shall be separated from adult offenders. In addition, the code in section 61 provides for release on licence whereby an offender can be prematurely released following a decree of the president of the republic.

Furthermore, there are several rights of prisoners protected in the Cameroonian criminal procedure code. These include; the right to fair trial⁷⁶; right to visits⁷⁷; the right to feeding⁷⁸; the right to decent physical and mental treatment⁷⁹; and the right to medical treatment⁸⁰. The enforcement of these rights is underpinned by section 122(5) which states that whoever violates or fails to comply with the provisions of section 122(1)-(4) or prevents their compliance with, shall be liable to prosecution without prejudice, where necessary, to disciplinary sanctions.

⁷⁶Section 8, 37 CPC

⁷⁷ Section 238 (1, *ibid*

⁷⁸ Section 122(4) *Ibid*

⁷⁹ Section 122(2) *Ibid.*

⁸⁰ Section 123 *Ibid*

Section 8 of the Criminal Procedure Code is outstanding in the protection of prisoners rights in Cameroon. The CPC identifies three categories of prisoners namely suspects⁸¹, defendants⁸² and accused persons⁸³. All of these persons are subject to detention. Nevertheless, the key right accorded to all these categories of prisoners is the right to a fair trial. This right has been examined under the universal as well as regional systems and pave the way for examination at the domestic level. The CPC protects the right to a fair trial by asserting the presumption of innocence of any prisoner who have committed a crime⁸⁴. Their guilt must only be established after they have been given all necessary guarantees necessary for their defence⁸⁵. The presumption of innocence applies to every suspect, defendant and accused⁸⁶.

The rights asserted by section 8 of the code are the right to consult a lawyer, the right to have a reasonable time to prepare his or her defence, right to legal aid in situations that the prisoner cannot afford the services of a counsel. As such, the spirit of th CPC appears to support the expeditious determination of cases. For instance, before the examining magistrates, the defendants appearing before them as well as trial judges have the right to a speedy trial, especially when in detention in prison as Justice V.B. Chi held in *The People v. Ashu Tande Daniel*.⁸⁷ In this case, the first accused had been in prison custody for over two years while the prosecution claimed that they were unable to serve their witnesses. This constitutes a perfect example of a violation of the prisoner's right to fair hearing, precisely the right to be tried within a reasonable time⁸⁸. Also, in *The People v. Asonganyi Nkeng Justin*⁸⁹ the accused was held under detention for over seven months without being summoned for hearing. This is a violation of the right to be heard promptly

⁸¹ As per section 9 (1) of the CPC, a suspect shall be a person against whom there exists any information or clue which tends to establish that he may have committed an offence or participated in its commission

⁸² Section 9(2) of the CPC defines a defendant to be any suspect who an examining magistrate notifies that he is presumed henceforth either as the offender or co-offender or as an accomplice.

⁸³ Section 9(3) of the CPC defines an accused person to be a person who must appear before the trial court to answer to the charge brought against him, whether in respect of a simple offence, a misdemeanour or felony.

⁸⁴ *Obiziako v. Commissioner of Police* (1964) NMLR 10; *Aruna v. The State* (1990) 6 NWLR 125.

⁸⁵ For instance, the right to counsel, and right to appeal among others.

⁸⁶ A suspect is any person against whom there exists any information which tends to establish that he may have committed an offence or participated in its commission; a defendant is any suspect whom an examining magistrate notifies that he is presumed henceforth either as offender or co-offender or as accomplice, while an accused is a person who must appear before the trial court to answer to the charge brought against him

⁸⁷ HCF/022c/2011.

⁸⁸ Faced with this scenario, it was further held that it amounted to an infringement of the criminal procedure code relating to the procedure for criminal actions which ought to attract a sanction of an absolute nullity under section 3 of the CPC. This decision is applauded as most judges intentionally keep accused persons in custody for inordinate length of time knowing quite well that it is a violation to human right to fair trial. The period of remand which did not appear in the various pieces of legislation which govern criminal procedure is now contained in section 221 of the CPC. Under this provision, the period of remand shall not exceed six months except by a reasoned ruling to 12 months in the case of a felony and six months for misdemeanour. Once these periods expire, the defendant must be released under pain of disciplinary sanctions against the examining magistrate under section 221(2) of the code

⁸⁹ Suit No. CFIB/522C/2013) Unreported.

or within a reasonable time as a requirement to enjoy the right to fair trial⁹⁰. Rights to visits and correspondences is strictly contemplated in the Cameroonian Criminal Procedure Code of 2005⁹¹.

Equally, law No 83/013 of 21st July 1983 relating to persons with disabilities in prisons of Cameroon. It accords them special attention while in detention relating to food, health care, clothing, visits among others. It is rather unfortunate that this category of persons are accommodated in the same cells with other prisoners. Neither are they given special health attention, feeding and clothing. As such, this amounts to no respect of the duty to respect, protect and fulfill the rights of persons with disability under detention.

Finally, decree No. 92/52 of 27th March 1992 on prison system in Cameroon details specific protections accorded prisoners. Article 29 of the 1992 decree on penitentiary administration and reforms in Cameroon provides that prisoners have the right to a daily meal which shall be balanced and sufficient to prevent prisoners from suffering from mal-nutrition and to provide them with the energy they need to maintain their health and carryout the work they are compelled to do. More so, the right to health is equally safeguarded. Article 32 and 34 in this regard posits that every detainee shall undergo a medical examination when taken into custody. In *Titiahongo v. Cameroon*⁹², the Human Rights Commission found Cameroon guilty for violating the prisoner's right to health by failing to provide him with timely and necessary medical care that resulted to his death.

6. CHALLENGES IN THE PROTECTION OF PRISONERS' RIGHTS

The initiatives of state actors to effectively protect detainees are hindered by a number of challenges due to the continuous violation of the rights. The challenges also account for the persistence of problems plaguing Cameroonian prisons.

6.1 Lack of adequate resources

Although international norms and standards provide that lack of resources shall not constitute a defence to a state for failing to respect, protect and fulfill the rights of its citizens, it is a major challenge that state actors in Cameroon face in the quest to protect

⁹⁰ In reaction to these recurrent acts, the Cameroon Bar Association on the 31st August, 2019 noted and condemned that lawyers have been consistently denied access to their clients and persons in various centers of detention namely the secretariat of state defence, prisons, police stations and gendarmerie brigades. The Bar association on similar basis noted that the rights of accused persons protected by national and international instruments ratified by Cameroon are constantly and consistently being violated by judicial authorities by way of: trial in a language they do not understand; violations of dignity of accused persons by bringing them naked to court; using torture as a means of getting evidence; illegal prolonged detention of detainees; transformation of judicial detention into administrative detention; frequent denial by state prosecutors to release accused persons when they are granted bail or being discharged by the court and recurrent refusal to acknowledge service of applicants made by lawyers to judicial authorities and refusal to respond to some applications from lawyers.

⁹¹ This right is contemplated by section 410 of the CPC which provides for the right to notification.

⁹² (2007) AHRLR 29.

the rights of detainees. Lack of resources results in the shortage of human personnel needed to work either as prison staff or as human rights activists under the state. It also takes the form of limited financial resources allocated to the department of penitentiary administration. For example, the South West Regional office of the National Commission for Human Rights and Freedoms has only 3 workers made of the Regional Secretary, one support staff and the office secretary. This gives them a big task to make frequent visits to the prisons which are spread all over the region like in Buea Central Prison, Kumba Principal Prison, Mamfe Principal Prison, Tiko, Muyuka and Limbe. This is coupled with the fact that they have other human rights issues to attend to vis-à-vis detainees. The end result of this is inefficiency and virtually no time to attend to other human rights issues⁹³.

Findings reveal that in relation to the department of penitentiary administration, the number of inmates outweighs that of prison staff. As such, instead of one staff taking care of just 5-15 inmates, the number is doubled to 30 and above. This is against the minimum rate prescribed by the UNSMRTP. In terms of financial resources, only the amount of 250FCFA is allocated to a detainee daily. That notwithstanding, what gets to the detainee is rated at 100FCFA. This amount is very insignificant for human subsistence daily. The end result of all this is that detainees suffer from malnutrition. The reason for the limited funds allocated to the prison sector is because the protection of detainees' rights does not form an economic priority to the state of Cameroon.

6.2 Lack of defined legal instruments

Cameroon is party to several international instruments protecting detainees' rights both at the universal and regional levels. Some of these include the universal declaration of human rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, the Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners, the Africa Charter on Human and People's Rights, among others. She has further domesticated these international norms and standards as part of her domestic laws by virtue of article 45 of the constitution. More so, human rights norms and standards have been asserted in the preamble of the constitution and the preamble as a matter of exception in Cameroon, form part and parcel of the constitution as per article 65.

One might argue that there is a plethora of legal instruments in Cameroon to protect detainees' rights. However, only the 1992 decree on prison administration specifically provide for the rights of prisoners. The rest of the domestic instruments do so implicitly. As such, it was a major recommendation of the Special Rapporteur on Prisons for Africa, following her visit in Cameroon in 2002 that there is dire need of legal

⁹³ According to the United State Department of State, bureau of human rights and labour, country report on human rights practices in 2024, page 25; NGOs, civil society, and the general population considered the NCHRF dedicated and effective, albeit inadequately funded and with insufficient ability to effectively hold human rights violators to account. Its budget was far smaller than that of most other agencies with comparable status, such as the National Anti-Corruption Commission and ELECAM

instruments to adequately provide for detainees' rights⁹⁴. But shockingly in 2019, 18 years after her visit, no legal instrument has been enacted. It is quite the contrary situation in South Africa, Ethiopia, and Senegal where detainees' rights are constitutionally protected and implemented alongside special prison regulations.

6.3 Administrative challenges

In any sector, there are procedures to carry on day-to-day affairs. This is not an exception to state actors that are engaged in the protection of detainees' rights. Both the department of penitentiary administration and the Human Rights Commission have administrative challenges that hinder the effective exercise of their functions in relation to prisoners. Taking the case of the NCHRF, it has a duty to promote and protect detainees. This is by carrying out frequent visits to detention centers and makes reports either appraising or condemning the state of human rights in Cameroon prisons. However, the commission does not have nor enjoy direct access to detention centers or prisons given that they must possess a written order from the state counsel of the jurisdiction giving them the authority to inspect prison conditions. This has been a major administrative setback to the commission as most attempts to get such order have failed or taken long periods before they are issued. For few instances this commission has had to visit prisons, it has condemned the poor state of prisons in terms of accommodation, health care, feeding, sanitation and long period of detention without trial.

6.4 Weak and politicized institutions

To provide for human rights at the universal, regional and domestic levels is one thing and to implement such norms and standards is another. Human rights are held to be given considerable recognition at the international level when compared to domestic level. Regardless of this, these norms serve no purpose in the absence of vibrant, democratic, non-politicized institutions to implement them. This is a serious problem in Cameroon. The 1990 law reforms saw the introduction of institutions to introduce democracy in Cameroon. The Human Rights Commission is one of such institutions. Although this commission is created by the government, it is expected to uphold a certain level of independence and must be impartial in the exercise of its functions.

Instead, the Cameroon Human Rights Commission lacks the requisite independence in the exercise of its duties, and lacks the necessary resources. As such, it remains weak and because of government influence it lacks the capacity to openly criticize the most barbaric human rights abuses occurring in Cameroon prisons⁹⁵. The reason is

⁹⁴The Ouagadougou Declaration on Accelerating Prison and Penal Reform in Africa (second pan-African Conference on Prison and Penal Reform in Africa, held in Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso from 18-20 September 2002) recommended that state parties should enact comprehensive law governing prisons and the implementation of punishment. Such law should be clear and unambiguous about the rights and duties of prisoners and prison officials. Officials should be trained to follow proper administrative procedures and to apply this law fairly. Administrative decisions that impact on the rights of prisoners should be subject to review by an independent and impartial judicial body.

⁹⁵To further show how weak, politicized and executively influenced the Cameroon Human Rights Commission is, it took this institution 6 months for it to gain access to Barrister Agbor Balla, Dr Neba

simple. The personnel are appointees of the Head of State and they pay allegiance to him rather than the population they are appointed to serve. Thus, the commission must be held to be accountable both to the detainees who are the focus of this study and to the entire Cameroonian community which is represented by parliament. The South African Human Rights Commission (SAHRC) and the Ugandan Human Rights Commission (UHRC) are glaring examples for the Cameroon NCHRF to emulate. Although set up and financed by their respective governments, these commissions enjoy a high degree of independence and possess judicial authority.

6.5 Lack of political will

This is a big challenge that affects the treatment of prisoners either negatively or positively. Where there is the political will, the state will definitely make resources available, especially financial resources for the improvement of prison conditions. Lack of political will by the state is equally seen in that very few policies are enacted coupled with very little discourse about ameliorating the conditions of prisoners at the domestic level. As earlier stated among the other challenges, the lack of political will is due to the fact that prisons do not form part of the Cameroon economic priority when put on the same scale with the development of the energy sector, technology, education and road infrastructure that form the basis of Cameroon anticipated emergence by 2035. This contributes to the poor implementation of the laws and amounts to Cameroon non-compliance with the triple pronged theory.

6.6 Attitudinal challenge by detainees

This challenge emanates from detainees themselves and those who work with them. Detainees have the perception that they constitute the last grade of humans in the community and often they do not want to be rehabilitated or are unwilling to be reintegrated back into their communities. As such, they go about from committing one crime to the other while in prison and when punished, they see the warders as their prime enemy and those who sentenced them to imprisonment or caused them to be detained. Thus, the lack of psychiatric personnel in the prison sector in Cameroon partially explains this challenge.

Nevertheless, faith-based organizations have taken up the challenge through constant preaching of the Gospel to detainees. This actually affects some detainees positively. When it comes to warders, although their training warrants them to treat detainees as humans or with respect to their human rights, most of them see detainees as inferior beings and this contributes to their high rate of torture in the Douala and the

Fontem, Mancho Bibixy following their illegal detention at the Yaounde Central Prison. These three persons are Anglophone Cameroonians who were brutally arrested on basis of causing riots, secession, and acts of terrorism in Anglophone Cameroon. This was as a result of their advocacy for the protection of common law system, the English educational system and identity of Former southern Cameroonians. The government in their usually manner of violating rights of Cameroonians, arrested them in Buea and Bamenda respectfully and taken to the political capital in Yaoundé where they were detained incommunicado for some time. The Cameroon Human Rights Commission, being an apolitical, independent body as it ought to be, stayed silent though given the mandate to promote and protect human rights.

Yaounde central Prison alongside the practice of solitary confinement. Torture here is both physical and psychological. The act of torture is a violation of customary international law and of course perpetrators of such an act ought to be punished. The practice of solitary confinement is equally prohibited under the Standard Minimum Rules for the treatment of detainees. The need for detainees to be treated on the basis of humanity and in accordance with article 10 of the ICCPR can only be achieved if there is a change in attitude by warders, detainees and the state too.

7. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

While Cameroon's protection and enforcement of detainees' rights partly comply with international norms and standards, there is still much work that needs to be done in the protection and enforcement of these rights. It is the responsibility of the state, the courts and the relevant stakeholders to change the society's perception that detainees have wronged the society and deserve to be punished. In other words, the courts need to remind the society that detainees upon their release become part of the society and that it is the society that benefits when detainees are released as rehabilitated members of the society.

It is crucial that the courts and the state adhere to their obligations under international law to respect, protect and fulfill detainees' rights without any form of discrimination as to status, race, ethnicity, nationality, language or any other factor. Though they have lost their right to liberty due to the incarceration, they are free to enjoy all other rights which they inherently possessed by virtue of their humanity. Their rights to a conducive and healthy environment, right to good food, healthcare, education as well as security should be guaranteed. This is because human rights reflect basic human needs which enhances human development. They deserve equal treatment in all domains of life as human beings.

Hence, the government of Cameroon is called upon to setup or enforce its obligations under international human right laws to guarantee the rights of prisoners and inspiration should be drawn from other jurisdictions on how they handle their prisoners such as South Africa which is hailed for respecting and protecting the rights of prisoners.

Human rights reflect basic human needs. They establish basic standards without which people cannot live in dignity. To violate someone's human rights is to treat that person as though he or she were not a human being. To advocate human rights is to demand that the human dignity of all people be respected. In claiming these human rights, everyone also accepts responsibilities: to respect the rights of others and to protect and support people whose rights are abused or denied. Discharging these responsibilities means claiming solidarity with all other human beings. All people everywhere have the same human rights which no one can take away. This is the basis of freedom, justice and peace in the world as advocated in the UDHR, 1948. All human rights are universal, indivisible, interdependent and interrelated. The international community must treat human rights globally in a fair and equal manner, on the same footing, and with the same emphasis. While the significance of national and regional particularities and various historical, cultural and religious backgrounds must be borne in mind, it is the duty of

States, regardless of their political, economic and cultural systems, to promote and protect all human rights and fundamental freedoms⁹⁶.

To recommend, this paper finds that the starting point in the protection of prisoners' rights is the incorporation of such rights in the constitution of the Republic of Cameroon. This is the practice in South Africa and she has been regarded to respect and protect prisoners' rights. This fact is supported by the manner South Africa treats prisoners in terms of accommodation, feeding, sanitation, education, health care, leisure, complaint mechanism and visits. This study therefore recommends that if Cameroon must start fulfilling her obligations to respect, protect and fulfil prisoners' rights as advocated in international human rights treaties ratified, she must copy the practice in South Africa.

Secondly, the role of the judiciary in the protection of prisoners' rights remain indispensable. As such, the empowerment of the judiciary to play its role in the proper interpretation of laws and respect of the principle of fair hearing would greatly help in the decongestion of prisons. This is feasible where in practice there is strict separation of powers among the three arms of government especially the non-interference of the executive in judicial affairs and guarantee of independence of the judiciary.

⁹⁶World Conference on Human Rights, Vienna 1993, paragraph 5.